

IMI2 821520 – ConcePTION

ConcePTION

**WP7 Information and
data governance,
ethics, technology, data
catalogue and quality
support**

D7.15 Final FAIR data catalogue

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Abstract

The objective of this final report is to summarize progress of the ConcePTION FAIR data catalogue (see Deliverable D7.7 and D7.6 for description and Deliverable D7.9 and D7.10 for test reviews, all deliverables are available at <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). The objective of the data catalogue is to collect summary level metadata on data sources and databanks and their mappings to the ConcePTION common data model and to aid ConcePTION partners in the execution of analyses to generate evidence on the safety of medicines in pregnancy (i.e. data elements and mapping catalogue). The design of this catalogue is based on the requirements analysis as delivered in D7.1 'User requirements and meta-data model for the FAIR data catalogue from WP1&2'.

In particular, the catalogue consists of sections for:

- Organisations - Contributors to the catalogue such as universities, companies, medical centres and research institutes
- Data sources - Collections of databanks covering the same population
- Databanks - Data collections such as registries, hospital discharge records, primary care medical records, or biobanks
- Networks - Collaborations of multiple institutions
- Common Data Models - Common Data Element models and Harmonization models
- Studies - Collaborations of multiple institutions, addressing research questions using data sources and/or databanks

In addition, we added supportive sections to describe the underlying data elements:

- Tables - Tables in databanks or models
- Variables - Variables in databanks or models
- TableMappings - Rule how common data model tables should be created from source tables
- VariableMappings - Rule how a common data model variables should be created from source variables

Based on the D7.10 a final round of improvements was implemented, in parallel to continued data updates. In addition, most focus has been on data maintenance. In addition, we published a perspective paper entitled "Towards an Interoperable Ecosystem of Research Cohort and Real-world Data Catalogues Enabling Multi-center Studies" in Yearbook of Medical Informatics (PMID: 36463884).

The Catalogue is an essential part of the ConcePTION pipeline, as illustrated in D7.5 (<https://zenodo.org/records/5829417#.YfraCerMK3A>) and in the ConcePTION wiki (<https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/ConceptionTools/wiki>).

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
CDM	Common Data
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
DAP	Data Access Partners
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
PID	Persistent Identifier

Introduction

As described in D7.7 and D7.6 the objective of the ConcePTION data catalogue is to allow researchers to identify relevant Data Access Partners (DAPs) and data sources for the conduct of studies to generate evidence on the safety of medicines used in pregnancy within the ConcePTION network. It also aims to enable ConcePTION partners to manage and transparently share meta-data on individual data items and their conversion to common elements (Common Data Model (CDM), or harmonization, as appropriate) as used in ConcePTION studies as part of federated study analyses. These elements will be delivered according to FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable principles. It is the intent to make the catalogue publicly available when the ConcePTION project ends, and we are currently investigating enablers and barriers from the Data Access Partners to do so.

The catalogue consists of two main areas hosting different data types and fulfilling different needs. The core are meta-data describing the DAP Organisation (Institution), the data source(s) the DAP has access to, the databanks within the data source and the individual data items contained within those databanks.

These concepts are described in Thurin *et al.* Briefly, the DAP organization may directly control or have access to many data sources. A data source is a collection of databanks. Databanks are a collection of structured healthcare data originated by an organization (normally, not a DAP) for their own primary purpose, where records are prompted whenever a specific event or healthcare interaction (e.g. diagnosis, medication dispensing, birth, death) occurs for persons in a specific population (underlying population of the databank). Databanks contain data items representing the details of the health record and interaction. A data source is a collection of databanks having the same underlying population, that the DAP has access to and can re-use for secondary purposes. Population-based healthcare or surveillance data are captured in the Catalogue in a separate section from data source of spontaneous pregnancy report.

Furthermore, in the case of population-based healthcare or surveillance data sources, the data dictionaries of the original data, and the design of their Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) process to the ConcePTION CDM are hosted in the Catalogue.

It must be remembered that the mapping to the ConcePTION CDM is only syntactic. The study-based decisions for semantic harmonization (mapping into a semantically harmonised

set of study specific variables) will be hosted in the future in the Studies section of the Catalogue.

These sections were developed and populated with data from several population-based healthcare DAPs. This report describes the user test of that Catalogue section for ConcePTION, built using MOLGENIS tools and software. For the purposes of this report, the users are key stakeholders within the project representing both DAPs who have to upload and view their meta-data and ConcePTION investigators querying the catalogue meta-data.

Methods

As extensively reported in the deliverable D7.1 and D7.6, the objective of the ConcePTION data catalogue is to serve the needs of ConcePTION partners to identify relevant data access partners and data sources for the conduct of studies to generate evidence on the safety of medicines in pregnancy and breastfeeding. For ConcePTION partners the catalogue will also be a repository to enable management and sharing of metadata on the individual data items and their mapping to the CDM. In the future, for example in a follow-up project, when the Studies section is implemented, the Catalogue will be a place to share data transformation tools, scripts, and decisions for the harmonisation to be used in ConcePTION studies. As such, the catalogue will serve as a key enabler of transparency around the ConcePTION data pipeline.

The work in this deliverable was based on the reviews from D7.10 and input from WP7 members, and revises the results reported in D7.7 (description of second catalogue prototype). The following improvements were implemented based on selected feedback:

Feedback on the data model and expected use of the catalogue by DAPs

- *“It would be good to see how databanks compose a data source. List of databanks in the data source and list of tables in the databank.”*
 - Change => a list of databanks is now shown for each data source, including indication of the type/family.
- *“We need more explanation of the links and relationships between the different blocks on the homepage. Introduction page with a glossary and a schematic?”*
 - Change => we have created a dashboard landing page.
- The relationships between institutions and other resources (databanks, data sources, networks) need to be defined more clearly:
 - *“ProviderOf [in an institution] is a mix of various different resources, but this is only clear when you go into an individual institution in Edit mode (“Query that lists all resources (data sources, databanks, cohorts, networks) that this institution is access provider of”). Until then it's not clear why there are different types of data in this list, and what ‘provider of’ actually means.”*
 - Change => removed providerOf and replaced with separate DAP and

partnership roles in resources.

- *“We need to define the link between a DAP and a data source e.g. University of Bordeaux as a DAP is the user of the French National Data (SNDS) so does that count as its ‘institute’?”*
 - Change => we created a separated DAP table detailing the relationship and also additional details such as clarification on what access the DAP enables.
- *“PartnerIn’ is also a mix of different resources. Surely institutes can only be a partner in a network? Are they ‘participants’ in a study (or do we need another word for this?)?”*
 - Change => we have reversed this relationship so the link can now be made from direction of ‘network’, ‘databank’, ‘data source’
- *“What’s the difference between the relationship data source<->institution and data source<-> DAP? You can add an institution in two different places within a data source and this is unclear.”*
 - Change => we have split the input making it clear if an institution is leading/partner in a data source, or if they are DAPs.
- *“We need clearer definitions of why particular resources belong to ‘providerOf’ and ‘partnerIn’”*
 - Change => these two relationships have been removed and replaced by separated DAP and partner relationships.

Feedback on population of the catalogue (now and in the future)

The DAPs currently have access to what is termed a ‘staging area’ to submit and review the metadata they hold in the catalogue before it is submitted into the catalogue and shared with all users of the catalogue. Review of their own rich metadata (metadata *about* an institution / data source / databank/data items), however, currently occurs in the central system in which edits to the variables in the staging areas are transferred. This prompted the following feedback:

- *“Who is entitled to change what?”*
 - Change => permissions managed via project management office
- *“Do we keep a change log?”*
 - Change => a change log has been implemented.
- *“What about sustainability in terms of input of data? Should DAPs be able to do this themselves?”*
 - Change => this is a future enhancement. We envision the catalogue to evolve into a ‘LinkedIn’ for data partners.

It became clear that not all meaning derived from the catalogue can be determined by the

software alone and that DAPs also have a role in ensuring that meaningful data is entered:

- *“Databanks need more meaningful names besides their acronyms.”*
 - Change => added names to the list of data banks, whenever DAPs include them.

Feedback on the user interface

Interviewees not directly involved in the design and construction of the catalogue were perfectly positioned to give their initial reaction to the catalogue and its user interface. Other interviewees could give more specific feedback with their own use cases in mind. Feedback received on the user interface was the following:

- *In the lists of resources such as Institutions / Data sources / Databanks, there should be standard columns in the initial presentation of a list. For example, “Add the name ‘ProviderOf’ as a standard column in the list of Institutions”, “Have the data source as a standard column in the databank list” or “I would like standard columns in the list of tables in a databank”.*
 - Change => we have revisited the default columns.

In line with the need described above for more explanation and context for users:

- *“Column headings could do with more explanation and more intuitive names – eg ‘ProviderOf’, what is this?”*
 - Change => better descriptions have been added.
- *“Short descriptions would be useful as an extra column when identifying eg databanks in the list”*
 - Change => in the data sources screen we have created a ‘nested’ table showing details of the linked databanks such as the databank family.

The use of the name ‘pid’ (‘Persistent Identifier’) as the key identifier for an institution / data source / databank was called into question since the field currently does not refer to an externally validated pid. The vision for the catalogue is that it will in the future use externally validated pids, and this will be addressed in due course.

- Change => we have changed this to enable ‘internal’ identifier that is easily understood by the data partner and ‘pid’ that is used as permanent id.

Recommendations from the online survey that were implemented:

- implement a shortcut to edit the current page
 - Change => this has been implemented.
- add a “go-back” function
 - Change => bread crumbs were added
- improve the explanations around how the different sections of the catalogue link together
 - Change => we made cross links shown as hyperlinks and enabled users to easily

- switch between sections
- additional filtering capabilities
 - Change => we improved the pre-configured filters

Results

The catalogue is described in detail in D7.7. In this report, we aim to highlight the upgraded features and most importantly, the many data updates until the submission of the present deliverable. The full system is available at <https://conception-acc.molgeniscloud.org/>. Access is granted via the ConcePTION project management office. The complete data model can be found in Appendix 1.

Data updates

We are grateful to the members of WP7, WP1 and WP2 and the rest of the consortium for a massive effort in data updates:

- Organisations 40 (was 32)
- Data sources 20 (was 7)
- Databanks 162 (was 18)
- Datasets 224 (previously known as ‘tables’, was 79)
- Networks 3 (was 1)
- Studies 16 (was 0)
- Data models 2 (was 3)
- Variables 5025 (was 458)
- Dataset mappings 36 (was 3)
- Variable mappings 468 (was 34)

Improved landing page

Based on user feedback we made the landing page more concise (Figure 1):

Data catalogue

Browse and manage metadata for data resources, such as cohorts, registries, biobanks, and multi-center collaborations thereof such as networks, common data models and studies.

Metadata on data collections

Organisations 40 Contributors to the catalogue such as departments from universities, companies, medical centres and research institutes	Data sources 20 Collections of data banks covering the same population	Databanks 162 Collections of data banks covering the same population
Networks 3 Collaborations of multiple organisations	Studies 16 Collaborations of multiple institutions, addressing research questions using data sources and/or data banks	Data models 2 Standard/harmonized data dictionaries for integrated analysis

Browse data definitions

Dataset and variable definitions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Datasets (224) • Variables (5025) 	Mappings to standards <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset mappings (36) • Variable mappings (468)
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Figure 1. Landing page in ConcePTION Data Catalogue

Improved list and search screens

Based on the feedback the list screens were improved as follows (Figure 2)

Data sources

filters columns download Table Search « < 1 - 20 of 20 > » Rows per page: (required) 20

#	+	id	name	website	lead organisation
		ARS	Tuscany Region Admin ... show more		ARS.TOSCANA
		Valencian Region	Valencian Region		
		LHU Caserta	LHU Caserta database		
		POMME	POMME		CHUT
		ISD	Scottish databanks		UoD
		EUROmediCAT	EUROmediCAT		ULST
		PHARMO	PHARMO Database Netw ... show more		PHARMO.I
		GePaRD	The German Pharmaco ... show more		BIPS
		SIDIAP	Sistema d'Informació ... show more		JORDIGOL
		SAIL	SAIL databank		USWAN
		MLT	Malta Congenital Ano ... show more		MLT.J
		THL	Finnish institute fo ... show more		THL.J
		Danish Health Data	Danish Health Data		
		Norwegian Health Data	Norwegian Health Dat ... show more		UiO
		MMC	Malformation Monitor ... show more		OVGU

type

Type to search

- Hospital discharge records
- Primary care medical records
- Pharmacy dispensing records
- Birth registry
- Induced terminations registry
- Congenital anomaly registry
- Population registry
- Registration with healthcare

system

- Hospital outpatient visit records
- Hospital inpatient records
- Emergency care discharge records
- Exemptions from co-payment
- Diagnostic tests or procedures

reimbursement

- Death registry
- Cancer registry
- Disease registry
- Vaccination registry
- Drug registry

Figure 2. Search and list screen on the ConcePTION Data Catalogue when user is allowed to edit.

Improved institution screen

In Figure 3, notice that we renamed 'institution' to 'organization' to be more inclusive, and we facilitated the more detailed listing of data sources the organization is involved:

Organisations
Show empty fields (N/A)

University of Oslo

PharmacoEpidemiology and Drug Safety Research Group (PharmaSafe) is a research group within the Department of Pharmacy at the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, UiO. The research group coordinates and performs studies of medications in pregnancy. First, PharmaSafe/UiO apply to the Regional Ethical Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REC)*. REC carries out an assessment as to whether research is undertaken in an acceptable manner. This entails the consideration of benefit versus risk for the participants and whether data protection is assured. UiOs Data Protection Officer performs the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). Upon approval from REC and the data protection officer at UiO, PharmaSafe/UiO applies to the administrator of each database for use of data files, and negotiates the terms and data transfer agreements. All data files are transferred from the different registries to UiO where it is uploaded to TSD, a secure platform for data storage and analysis (GDPR compliant). On TSD, the data files from the different registries are linked using the Norwegian national identity number. International researchers can access the data through TSD or sign a data transfer agreement with UiO and have data transferred abroad. There are some restrictions on the types of data that can be transferred abroad. The data themselves are free of charge, but costs accrue for administrative handling and file processing.

Id: UiO

Acronym: UiO

Name: University of Oslo

Type: Academic institution

Country: Norway

Leading resources:

id	pid	acronym	name	website	additional organisations	description	external identifiers	contacts
MBRN		MBRN	MBRN			Medical Birth Regist ... show more		
NOPR		NPR	Norwegian Patient Re ... show more			Danish National pati ... show more		

Figure 3. Organization screen (formerly known as institution) of the ConcePTION Data Catalogue

Data source screen

The improved data source screen (Figure 4). Notice the details of the databanks (below) included:

The screenshot shows the 'Data sources' page for 'Tuscany Region Administrative Databases' in the ConcePTION Data Catalogue. The page includes a navigation bar with 'conception / catalogue / datasources / ARS', a user profile 'Hi admin', and a 'Sign out' button. The main content area is titled 'Tuscany Region Administrative Databases' and contains a detailed description of the data source. Below the description are several sections: 'overview', 'population', 'contents', and 'linkage'. The 'linkage' section features a table of linked resources with columns for name, databank family, linkage strategy, linkage description, and linkage variable.

General information

- Id:** ARS
- Acronym:** ARS
- Name:** Tuscany Region Administrative Databases
- Lead organisation:** ARSTOSCANA
- Description:** As is the case in every Italian region, the reason for entering the database is the registration with a primary care physician, which may happen upon immigration or upon birth; the reason for exiting the database is emigration or death. Beyond administrative databanks, for the same underlying population other data banks are collected by the Tuscany Region or by other Tuscan organizations: the birth registry, the spontaneous abortions and induced terminations registry, the death registry, the vaccine registry, the pathology registry, the registry of primary care community centers, the COVID registry, the congenital anomaly registry and the rare disease registry. Medical records and/or laboratory results are collected by local organizations, such as hospital, on subsets of the underlying Tuscan population.

linked resources:

name	databank family	linkage strategy	linkage description	linkage variable
AP				
covid registry (COVID_DATASET)	Disease registry			
ARS_PS				
SPA				
SALM				
RMR				
Community primary care centers administrative records (SPC)				

Figure 4. Data source screen of the ConcePTION Data Catalogue

Improved Mappings/ETL screen

We are particularly proud of the new data mapping screen, that fully implements the format of the ‘ETL specification tables’ adopted in the ConcePTION data pipeline (Figure 5):

home / datasetmappings /

Dataset mapping

Source table: SDO

Source table: PROCEDURES

Description:
For each record ● Extract from VISIT_OCCURRENCE (above) the corresponding value of visit_occurrence_id ● Create a record of EVENTS for each non CODCHI, CODCHI2,...,CODCHI6; for each of them, copy the content of the cell in the column code_event, and copy ● Copy the values of SDO into EVENT following table

[Download ETL as csv](#)
[Download ETL as Excel](#)

#	Target column	Source column	Description
	meaning_of_procedure		procedure_during_hospita
	origin_of_procedure		'SDO'
	person_id	SDO.iduni	
	procedure_code	SDO.codchi2SDO.codchi3SDO.codchi4SDO.codchi5SDO.codchi6SDO.codchi4	As explained above
	procedure_code_vocabulary		ICD9PROC
	procedure_date	SDO.datchi6SDO.datchi5SDO.datchi4SDO.datchi3	Respectively per CODCHI,...,CODCHI6
	visit_occurrence_id		As explained above

Figure 5. Mapping screen of the ConcePTION Data Catalogue

Migration of WP2 catalogue to WP7 catalogue platform

Data capture forms and metadata already available within WP2 catalogue has been partially migrated to WP7 catalogue operating server to facilitate its sustainability.

Discussion

In November 2020, the MINERVA (Metadata for data discoverability and study replicability in observational studies) project (EUPAS39322) was initiated in response to the Heads of Medicines Agencies–European Medicines Agency (HMA-EMA) joint Big Data Task Force recommendation on “the identification of metadata” for regulatory decision-making on the choice of data source. The ConcePTION Catalogue was also extensively used as a reference in the deliverables of the MINERVA Project. Based on the results of the MINERVA Project, the HMA-EMA catalogues of real-world data sources and studies was launched in January 2024. Following the MINERVA recommendation, the HMA-EMA catalogue plans to set up persistent identifiers for data sources and facilitate interoperability with other Catalogues. The ambition is that the ConcePTION Catalogue in the future will enable such interoperability. Moreover, the international association VAC4EU (Vaccine monitoring Collaboration for Europe) has a data Catalogue (vac4eu.org/catalogue/) which is designed to be interoperable with the ConcePTION Catalogue

Conclusion

The latest updates to ConcePTION Data Catalogue represent a significant advancement on how to effectively navigate the data sources participating in ConcePTION. Several enhancements to the visualization of the catalogue were made possible thanks to the users' input. Currently, we are exploring a merger of the ConcePTION catalogue with the long-term maintained evolution of the MOLGENIS catalogue at <http://data-catalogue.molgenisccloud.org> . We thank all interviewees and reviewers for their time and great input.

References

Thurin NH, Pajouheshnia R, Roberto G, et al. From Inception to ConcePTION: Genesis of a Network to Support Better Monitoring and Communication of Medication Safety During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 2022;111(1):321-331. doi:10.1002/cpt.2476

Swertz M, van Enckevort E, Oliveira JL, et al. Towards an Interoperable Ecosystem of Research Cohort and Real-world Data Catalogues Enabling Multi-center Studies. *Yearb Med Inform.* 2022;31(1):262-272. doi:10.1055/s-0042-1742522

Appendix: updated data model

Schema documentation for 'conception'

Table: All variables

Generic listing of all source variables. Should not be used directly, please use SourceVariables or RepeatedSourceVariables instead

Table 'All variables' has the following subclasses/specializations:

All variables

Generic listing of all source variables. Should not be used directly, please use SourceVariables or RepeatedSourceVariables instead

Repeated variables (extends:) - Definition of a repeated sourceVariable. Refers to another variable for its definition

Variables (extends:) - Definition of a non-repeated variable, or of the first variable from a repeated range

Column definitions:

resource - Data source that this variable was collected in
 domain: All variables
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

dataset - Dataset this variable is part of
 domain: All variables
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Datasets, refLink=resource) required

name - name of the variable, unique within a table
 domain: All variables
 constraints: key=1string required

label - Human friendly longer name, if applicable
 domain: All variables
 constraints: string

collection event - in case of protocolised data collection this defines the moment in time this variable is collected on
 domain: All variables
 constraints: ref(conception.Collection events)

since version - When this variable was introduced
 domain: All variables
 constraints: string

until version - When this variable was removed if applicable
 domain: All variables
 constraints: string

format - Data type, e.g. string,int,decimal,date,datetime etc

domain: Variables

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Formats)

unit

domain: Variables

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Units)

references - to define foreign key relationships between variables within or across tables

domain: Variables

constraints: ref(conception.All variables, refLink=resource)

mandatory - whether this variable is required within this collection

domain: Variables

constraints: bool

description

domain: Variables

constraints: text

order - to sort variables you can optionally add an order value

domain: Variables

constraints: int

example values

domain: Variables

constraints: string_array

permitted values

domain: Variables

constraints: reback(conception.Variable values, refBack=variable)

keywords

domain: Variables

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Keywords)

repeats - listing of all repeated variables defined for this variable

domain: Variables

constraints: reback(conception.Repeated variables, refBack=is repeat of)

vocabularies

domain: Variables

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Vocabularies)

notes - Any other information on this variable

domain: Variables

constraints: text

mappings - in case of protocolised data collection this defines the moment in time this variable is collected on

domain: All variables
constraints: refback(conception.Variable mappings, refBack=target variable)

is repeat of - reference to the definition of the sourceVariable that is being repeated
domain: Repeated variables
constraints: ref(conception.Variables, refLink=resource) required

Table: Collection events

Definition of a data collection event for a resource

Column definitions:

resource - Resource this collection event is part of
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

name - Name of the collection event
constraints: key=1string required

description - Description of the collection event
constraints: text

subcohorts - Subcohorts that are targetted by this collection event
constraints: ref_array(conception.Subcohorts, refLink=resource)

start year - Start year of data collection
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Years)

start month - Start month of data collection
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Months)

end year - End year of data collection. Leave empty if collection is ongoing
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Years)

end month - End month of data collection. Leave empty if collection is ongoing
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Months)

age groups - Age groups included in this data collection event
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups)

number of participants - Number of participants sampled in this data collection event
constraints: int

areas of information - Areas of information that were extracted in this data collection event
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Areas of information cohorts)

data categories - Methods of data collection used in this collection event
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Data categories)

sample categories - Samples that were collected in this collection event
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Sample categories)

standardized tools - Standardized tools, e.g. surveys, questionnaires, instruments used to collect data for this collection event

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Standardized tools)

standardized tools other - If 'other', please specify

constraints: string

core variables - Name 10-20 relevant variables that were collected in this collection event

constraints: string_array

supplementary information - Any other information that needs to be disclosed for this collection event

constraints: text

Table: Contacts

Column definitions:

resource - Resource the contact is affiliated with

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Resources) required

role - Type(s) of contribution or role in the resource

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Contribution types)

role description - Description of the role

constraints: text

first name - First name of the contact person

constraints: key=1string required

last name - Last name of the contact person

constraints: key=1string required

prefix - Surname prefix, if applicable

constraints: string

initials - Initials of the contact person

constraints: string

title - Title of the contact person

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Titles)

organisation - Affiliated organisation of the contact person

constraints: ref(conception.Organisations)

email - Contact's email address

constraints: string

orcid - Orcid of the contact person

constraints: string

homepage - Link to contact's homepage
 constraints: string

photo - Contact's photograph
 constraints: file

expertise - Description of contact's expertise
 constraints: string

Table: DAPs

Data access provider relationship where an institution can provide access to (parts of) a resource

Column definitions:

organisation - Institution that provides access
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Organisations) required

resource - Resource that is access or has experience with provided to
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Resources) required

population subset other - If 'other' is selected above, describe the subset that can be accessed
 constraints: text

is data access provider - Description of population subset, data access levels, completeness, reason for access
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.DAP information)

reason access other - If reason access is 'other', reason for being able to access (an extract of) the data source
 constraints: text

process time - On average, how many DAYS does it take for approval/access to be obtained following an application for data access?
 constraints: int

Table: Dataset mappings

Column definitions:

source - datasource being mapped from
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

source dataset - name of the table being mapped from
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Datasets, refLink=source) required

target - model being mapped to, i.e. toModel.resource + toModel.version

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

target dataset - name of the table being mapped to
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Datasets, refLink=target) required

order - Order in which table ETLs should be executed for this source-target combination
constraints: int

description - human readable description of the mapping
constraints: text

syntax - formal definition of the mapping, ideally executable code
constraints: text

Table: Datasets

Definition of a dataset within a (common) data model

Column definitions:

resource - resources that these variables are part of
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

name - unique dataset name in the model
constraints: key=1string required

label - short human readable description
constraints: string

unit of observation - defines what each record in this table describes
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Observation targets)

keywords - enables grouping of table list into topic and to display tables in a tree
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Keywords)

description - description of the role/function of this table
constraints: text

number of rows - count of the number of records in this table
constraints: int

mapped to - common dataset models this dataset has been mapped into
constraints: reback(conception.Dataset mappings, refBack=source dataset)

mapped from - source datasets that have been mapped to this harmonized dataset
constraints: reback(conception.Dataset mappings, refBack=target dataset)

since version - When this dataset was introduced
constraints: string

until version - When this dataset was removed if applicable

constraints: string

Table: Documentation

Documentation attached to a resource

Column definitions:

resource - The resource this documentation is for
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

name - Document name
constraints: key=1string required

type - Type of documentation
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Document types)

description - Description of the document
constraints: text

url - Hyperlink to the source of the documentation
constraints: string

file - Optional file attachment containing the documentation
constraints: file

Table: External identifiers

Column definitions:

resource - Resource that this external identifier belongs to
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

identifier - External identifier
constraints: key=1text required

external identifier type - External identifier type
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.External identifier types)

external identifier type other - If other, enter external identifier type
constraints: text

Table: Linked resources

Links between datasource and databank

Column definitions:

main resource
constraints: key=1ref(conception.RWE resources) required

linked resource

constraints: key=1ref(conception.RWE resources) required

other linked resource - If other linked data source, enter the name of the data source

constraints: text

linkage strategy - The linkage method that was used to link data banks. One entry per data bank

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Linkage strategies)

linkage variable - If a single variable (or linkage key) is used to link a data bank to others, a name and description of the variable is provided. One entry per data bank

constraints: text

linkage variable unique - If a single variable is used to link a data bank to others, is the variable a unique identifier? One entry per data bank

constraints: bool

linkage completeness - Provide a high-level description of the completeness of linkages that are currently available between data banks in the data source (max 100 words)

constraints: text

pre linked - Does the data source constitute of linked data sources?

constraints: bool

Table: Mappings

Mapping from collected datasets to standard/harmonized datasets, optionally including ETL syntaxes

Column definitions:

source - Data source that is being mapped to a (common) data model

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

source version - version of the datasource that is being mapped

constraints: string required

target - model being mapped to

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Models) required

target version - version of the model being mapped to

constraints: string required

mapping status - Mapping from collected datasets to standard/harmonized datasets, optionally including ETL syntaxes

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Mapping status)

ETL frequency - The frequency of the ETL process, in months

constraints: int

Table: Publications

Publications following bibtex format

Column definitions:

- doi - Digital object identifier
constraints: key=1string required
- title - Publication title
constraints: text
- authors - List of authors, one entry per author
constraints: string_array
- year - Year of publication (or, if unpublished, year of creation)
constraints: int
- journal - Journal or magazine the work was published in
constraints: string
- volume - Journal or magazine volume
constraints: int
- number - Journal or magazine issue number
constraints: int
- pagination - Page numbers, separated either by commas or double-hyphens
constraints: string
- publisher - Publisher's name
constraints: string
- school - School where the thesis was written (in case of thesis)
constraints: string
- abstract - Publication abstract
constraints: text
- resources - List of resources that refer to this publication
constraints: refback(conception.Extended resources, refBack=publications)

Table: Quantitative information

Quantitative information on the resource

Column definitions:

- resource
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

age group - Select the relevant age group for this quantitative information
constraints: key=1ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups) required

population size - Total number of unique individuals with records captured in the data source (most recent count). In the catalogue, this will accommodate counts per year
constraints: int

active size - Number of unique, active, or currently registered individuals with records captured in the data source (most recent count). In the catalogue, this will accommodate counts per year
constraints: int

no individuals with samples - Number of unique individuals with records of biological samples (e.g., blood, urine) (most recent count). In the catalogue, this will accommodate counts per year
constraints: int

mean observation years - Median years for which unique individuals with records captured in the data source are observable (most recent count)
constraints: int

mean years active - Median time for which unique individuals with records captured in the data source are observable (most recent count)
constraints: int

median age - Median age of individuals within data source
constraints: int

proportion female - Proportion of females in the data source
constraints: int

Table: Resources

Generic listing of all resources. Should not be used directly, instead use specific types such as Databanks and Studies

Extended table definitions:

Table 'Resources' has the following subclasses/specializations:

Resources

Generic listing of all resources. Should not be used directly, instead use specific types such as Databanks and Studies

Extended resources (extends:)

Organisations (extends:) - Research departments and research groups

Data resources (extends:) - Resources for data

Models (extends:) - Data models

Networks (extends:) - Collaborations of multiple institutions

Studies (extends:) - Collaborations of multiple institutions, addressing research questions using data sources and/or data banks

Cohorts (extends:) - Group of individuals sharing a defining demographic characteristic

RWE resources (extends:) - Real world data collections

Data sources (extends:) - Collections of multiple data banks covering the same population

Databanks (extends:) - Data collection from real world databases such as health records, registries

Column definitions:

heading: overview - General information

id - Internal identifier
domain: Resources
constraints: key=1string required

pid - Persistent identifier
domain: Resources
constraints: key=2string

acronym - Acronym if applicable
domain: Resources
constraints: string

name - Name used in European projects
domain: Resources
constraints: key=3text required

local name - If different from above, name in the national language
domain: Data resources
constraints: string

type - Type of organisation; in which sector is the organisation active?
domain: Organisations
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Organisation types)

type other - If type is 'other', a description of type of organisation
domain: Organisations
constraints: text

institution - University, company, medical centre or research institutes this organisation is part of
domain: Organisations
constraints: text

institution acronym - Short name of the organisation

domain: Organisations

constraints: string

email - Contact email address for person responsible for organization entry in catalogue

domain: Organisations

constraints: email

logo - Logo of the organisation

domain: Organisations

constraints: file

address - Address of the organisation

domain: Organisations

constraints: text

expertise - A short description of the expertise of this institution

domain: Organisations

constraints: text

country - Country in which the institution head office or coordinating centre is located

domain: Organisations

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Countries)

features - Features that describe this organisation

domain: Organisations

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Organisation features)

role - Roles of the institution in connection with data sources in the catalogue. Select one or more of the following:

domain: Organisations

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Organisation roles)

leading resources - Listing of data sources, cohorts, studies (etc)

domain: Organisations

constraints: reback(conception.Extended resources, refBack=lead organisation)

additional resources - Listing of data sources, cohorts, studies (etc)

domain: Organisations

constraints: reback(conception.Extended resources, refBack=additional organisations)

type - Type of network, e.g. h2020 project

domain: Networks

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Network types)

features - Characterizations of the network

domain: Networks

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Network features)

- type - Select 1 of the following types of study
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Study types)
- type other - If other, describe the type of study
domain: Studies
constraints: string
- type - Which of the following families of databanks best describe this data source
domain: RWE resources
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Datasource types)
- type other - If other, describe the type of datasource
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- keywords - Keywords to increase findability of this resource. Try to use words that are not used in the description
domain: Data resources
constraints: text
- website - Link to the website or homepage
domain: Resources
constraints: hyperlink
- lead organisation - lead organisation (e.g. research department or group) for this resource
domain: Extended resources
constraints: ref_array(conception.Organisations)
- additional organisations - List the names of any additional organisations that contributed to the resource
domain: Extended resources
constraints: ref_array(conception.Organisations)
- other organisations - List the names of any other organisations that are not listed and contributed to this resource
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- other organisations - List the names of any other organisations that are not listed and contributed to this resource
domain: Networks
constraints: text
- description - Short description
domain: Resources
constraints: text
- data collection description - Describe the process of collection and recording of data.
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text

date established - Date when the data source was first established. If the exact day of the month is not known, please enter 15. If the exact month is not known then please enter 15/06

domain: RWE resources

constraints: date

start data collection - The date when data started to be collected or extracted. If the exact day of the month is not known, please enter 15. If the exact month is not known then please enter 15/06

domain: RWE resources

constraints: date

end data collection - If data collection in the data source has ceased, on what date did new records last enter the data source?. If the exact day of the month is not known, please enter 15. If the exact month is not known then please enter 15/06

domain: RWE resources

constraints: date

time span description - Description of time span

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

external identifiers - External identifier(s) for this resource (e.g. EUPASS number, UMCG register number)

domain: Extended resources

constraints: reback(conception.External identifiers, refBack=resource)

status - Status of the study

domain: Studies

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Study status)

release frequency - Refreshing rate (in months)

domain: Models

constraints: int

contact email - Contact e-mail address for this cohort

domain: Cohorts

constraints: string

contacts - Contact person(s)

domain: Resources

constraints: reback(conception.Contacts, refBack=resource)

type - Type of resource, e.g. registry, cohort, biobank

domain: Cohorts

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Resource types)

type other - If other, describe the type of resource

domain: Cohorts

constraints: string

- design - The study design of this cohort, i.e. cross-sectional or longitudinal
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Cohort designs)
- design description - Short description of the study design of this cohort
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: text
- design schematic - A schematic depiction of the study design of this cohort
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: file
- collection type - The data collection type of this cohort, i.e. retrospective or prospective; if both, select both
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Collection types)
- logo - Logo of the resource, for use on homepages etc.
 domain: Extended resources
 constraints: file
- heading: population - Description of the population that can potentially be captured in the resource
- number of participants - Total number of individuals for which data is collected
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: int
- number of participants with samples - Number of individuals for which samples are collected
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: int
- underlying population - Provide a summary description of the underlying population (maximum 100 words) or URL to a description
 domain: Databanks
 constraints: text
- countries - Countries where data from this resource largely originate from
 domain: Extended resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Countries)
- regions - Geographical regions where data from this resource largely originate from
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Regions)
- population age groups - Which population age groups are captured in this resource? Select all that are relevant.
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups)
- inclusion criteria - Inclusion criteria applied to the participants of this resource

domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Inclusion criteria)

other inclusion criteria - Other inclusion criteria applied to the participants of this resource

domain: Cohorts
 constraints: text

start year - Year when first data was collected

domain: Cohorts
 constraints: int

end year - Year when last data was collected. Leave empty if collection is ongoing

domain: Cohorts
 constraints: int

start year - Year when the network was created

domain: Networks
 constraints: int

end year - Year when the network ended

domain: Networks
 constraints: int

population entry - Select the possible causes / events that trigger the registration of a person in the data source

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Population entry)

population entry other - If other, specify the causes of entry to the underlying population

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: text

population exit - Select the possible causes / events that trigger the de-registration of a person in the data source

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Population exit)

population exit other - If other, specify the causes of exit from the underlying population

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: text

population disease - Does the resource collect information on a specific disease subpopulation (e.g., as in a disease-specific registry)?

domain: Data resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Diseases)

population oncology topology - Does the resource collect information on specific cancer subtype(s)? If yes, select topology specifications.

domain: Data resources

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.ICDO topologies)

population oncology morphology - Does the resource collect information on specific cancer subtype(s)? If yes, select morphology specifications.

domain: Data resources

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.ICDO morphologies)

population coverage - Estimated percentage of the population covered by the data source in the catchment area. Please describe the denominator.

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

population not covered - Description of the population covered by the data source in the catchment area whose data are not collected, where applicable (e.g.: people who are registered only for private care)

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

quantitative information - Numerical summaries describing data bank population

domain: RWE resources

constraints: reback(conception.Quantitative information, refBack=resource)

subcohorts - List of subcohorts or subpopulations for this resource

domain: Cohorts

constraints: reback(conception.Subcohorts, refBack=resource)

heading: contents - Data model and contents

datasets

domain: Extended resources

constraints: reback(conception.Datasets, refBack=resource)

mappings to data models - overview of dataset mappings available

domain: RWE resources

constraints: reback(conception.Dataset mappings, refBack=source)

areas of information - Areas of information that were collected

domain: RWE resources

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Areas of information ds)

quality of life other - If other, specify additional quality of life measures

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

cause of death code other - If 'other,' what cause of death vocabulary is used?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

indication vocabulary other - If 'other,' what indication for use vocabulary is used?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

- genetic data vocabulary other - If 'other,' what genetic data vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- care setting other - If 'other,' description of the setting of care
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- medicinal product vocabulary other - If 'other,' description of the medicinal product
vocabulary
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- prescriptions vocabulary other - If 'other,' what vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- dispensings vocabulary other - If 'other,' what vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- procedures vocabulary other - If 'other,' what vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- biomarker data vocabulary other - If 'other,' what vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- diagnosis medical event vocabulary other - If 'other,' what vocabulary is used?
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- data dictionary available - Are a data dictionary and a data model available?
domain: Databanks
constraints: bool
- disease details - If data on a specific disease is collected, which diseases does the
data source collect information on
domain: RWE resources
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.MedDRA)
- disease details other - Specify disease details if not present in MedDRA
domain: RWE resources
constraints: text
- biospecimen collected - If the data bank contains biospecimens, what types of
specimen
domain: RWE resources
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Biospecimens)
- languages - Languages in which that the records are recorded (in ISO 639,

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_ISO_639-1_codes)

domain: RWE resources

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Languages)

record trigger - What triggers the creation of a record in the data bank? e.g., hospital discharge, specialist encounter, dispensation of a medicinal product, recording of a congenital anomaly

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

collection events - List of collection events defined for this resource

domain: Cohorts

constraints: reback(conception.Collection events, refBack=resource)

unit of observation - Based on the prompt, what is the unit of observation of a record (e.g., person, prescription)?

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

multiple entries - Can there be multiple entries for a single person in the data bank? For example, may a person contribute multiple records to the data bank?

domain: Databanks

constraints: bool

heading: linkage - Data linkage

has identifier - Is there a unique identifier for a person in the data bank?

domain: Databanks

constraints: bool

identifier description - Describe the variable that is used as a unique identifier for a person in the data bank? If the unique identifier is not at level of a person (for example hospital encounter), describe how this translated to an individual level

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

linkage description - Provide a high-level description of the linkages that are either: currently available between data sources in the data source (when pre-linked = yes); linkages that are possible when using the data source

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

linkage possibility - Can this data source be linked to other data sources?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: bool

linked resources - List of resources that are linked into this main resource

domain: RWE resources

constraints: reback(conception.Linked resources, refBack=main resource)

release type - Select whether this resource is a closed dataset or whether new data is released continuously or at a termly basis

- domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Release types)
- release description - Description of the release cycle of this resource
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: text
- linkage options - Linkage options with additional data sources that are available for this resource
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: text
- heading: access - Access and validation information
- data holder - The name of the organisation that is responsible for governance of the data bank
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: ref(conception.Organisations)
- DAPs - List of DAPs that are listed in the catalogue as having (conditional) permission to access (an extract of) the data resource
 domain: Data resources
 constraints: reffback(conception.DAPs, refBack=resource)
- reason sustained - Description of the reason why the data bank is sustained by the organisation (e.g., for surveillance, clinical purposes, financial or administrative purposes, research purposes)
 domain: Databanks
 constraints: text
- data access conditions - Codes defining data access terms and conditions
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Data access conditions)
- data use conditions - Codes defining data use terms and conditions
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Data use conditions)
- data access conditions description - Description of data access terms and use conditions
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: text
- data access fee - Does a fee apply to gain access to data of this cohort?
 domain: Cohorts
 constraints: bool
- informed consent - Is informed consent required for use of the data for research purposes?
 domain: RWE resources
 constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Informed consents)

informed consent other - If other, describe the conditions when informed consent is required

domain: RWE resources
constraints: text

access identifiable data - Can identifiable data be accessed in the data bank (including patient/practitioner name/practice name)?

domain: RWE resources
constraints: text

access identifiable data route - If yes above, what is the route to access or process this information? What permission is required?

domain: RWE resources
constraints: text

access subject details - Can individual patients/practitioners/practices be contacted in the data bank?

domain: RWE resources
constraints: bool

access subject details route - If yes above, what is the route to access or process this information? What permission is required?

domain: RWE resources
constraints: text

audit possible - Are external parties allowed to audit the data? For example, is it possible for an external party to audit the quality or validity of the data source?

domain: RWE resources
constraints: bool

access third party - Can (an extract of) the data bank be accessed with permission by a third party?

domain: Databanks
constraints: bool

access third party conditions - If above is 'yes', describe the conditions under which third-party access may be granted

domain: Databanks
constraints: text

access non EU - Can (an extract of) the data bank be accessed with permission by a non-EU/EEA institution?

domain: Databanks
constraints: bool

access non EU conditions - If yes above, describe the conditions under which non-EU/EEA access may be granted

domain: Databanks
constraints: text

standard operating procedures - Is there a standard operating procedure document that defines the processes and procedures for data capture and management?

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: bool

biospecimen access - If the data bank contains biospecimens (e.g., tissue samples), can these be retrieved?

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: bool

biospecimen access conditions - If yes above, describe the conditions under which permission to retrieve biospecimens may be granted

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: text

governance details - If available, provide a link to documents or webpages that describe the overall governance of the data source bank (governing data access or utilisation for research purposes by existing DAPs)

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: text

approval for publication - Is an approval needed to publish the results of a study using the data

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: bool

heading: updates - Information on the regularity of updates and time lags

refresh - Average number of days between refresh of data bank with new records

domain: Databanks
 constraints: int

lag time - How many days is the lag time after refresh before a record can be extracted? (e.g., a lag time may occur if the originator conducts quality checks)

domain: Databanks
 constraints: int

preservation - Are records preserved in the data bank indefinitely?

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: bool

preservation duration - If no to the above, for how long (in years) are records preserved in the data bank?

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: int

refresh period - If data are refreshed on fixed dates (e.g., every June and December), when are the refreshes scheduled? Select all that apply from the following:

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Refresh periods)

date last refresh - Date of last update/refresh

domain: RWE resources
 constraints: date

heading: quality - List of relevant studies conducted using the data bank

qualification - Has the data source successfully undergone a formal qualification process (e.g., from the EMA, or ISO or other certifications)?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: bool

qualifications description - Has the resource successfully undergone a qualification process (e.g., from the EMA)? If yes, describe the qualification(s) granted

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

number of records - Total number of unique records captured in the data bank (most recent count)

domain: Databanks

constraints: int

completeness - Describe the completeness of the data bank (e.g., variables with more or fewer missing values)

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

completeness over time - Describe any changes in completeness of the data bank (e.g., variables with more or fewer missing values) that have occurred over time

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

completeness results - What methods or processes are applied to check completeness of the data bank?

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

quality description - Describe the quality of the data bank (e.g., variables with more or fewer missing values)

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

quality over time - Describe any changes in quality of the data bank that have occurred over time

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

access for validation - Can validity of the data in the data bank be verified, e.g., by review of origin medical charts?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: bool

quality validation frequency - How often are data quality checks and validation steps conducted on the data bank?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

quality validation methods - What methods or processes are applied for data quality checks and validation steps conducted on the data bank?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

correction methods - What methods or processes are applied to correct illogical values in the data bank?

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

quality validation results - If available, provide a link to a publication of the data quality check and validation results

domain: RWE resources

constraints: string

heading: standards - Use of standard data models and ontologies

cdms - Common data models used or ETL-ed to by this data source

domain: RWE resources

constraints: refback(conception.Mappings, refBack=source)

cdms other - If not in list above, give the name of cdm(s) used by this data source

domain: RWE resources

constraints: text

ETL standard vocabularies - Are data mapped to standardised vocabularies during ETL to the CDM? If yes, what vocabularies are used for events, such as diagnoses?

domain: Databanks

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Vocabularies)

ETL standard vocabularies other - If other, what other vocabularies are used?

domain: Databanks

constraints: text

heading: information - Other information

design paper - Publication(s) that describe(s) the design of this resource

domain: Data resources

constraints: ref_array(conception.Publications)

publications - Other publication(s) about this resource

domain: Extended resources

constraints: ref_array(conception.Publications)

informed consent type - What type of informed consent was given for data collection?

domain: Data resources

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Informed consent types)

funding sources - Specify the main financial support sources for the data source in the last 3 years. Select all that apply

domain: RWE resources

- constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Funding types)
- funding scheme - The source of funding for the study. Select all that apply
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study funding)
- funding statement - Statement listing funding that was obtained for this resource
domain: Extended resources
constraints: text
- acknowledgements - Acknowledgement statement and citation regulation for this resource
domain: Extended resources
constraints: text
- documentation - Descriptive document(s) available for this resource, e.g. informed consent
domain: Extended resources
constraints: reback(conception.Documentation, refBack=resource)
- supplementary information - Any other information that needs to be disclosed for this resource
domain: Data resources
constraints: text
- heading: collaborations - List of relevant collaborations
- studies - Listing of studies that used this cohort
domain: Cohorts
constraints: reback(conception.Studies, refBack=cohorts)
- networks - The consortia or networks that this cohort is involved in
domain: Cohorts
constraints: reback(conception.Networks, refBack=cohorts)
- networks - The consortia or networks that this study is part of
domain: Studies
constraints: ref_array(conception.Networks)
- networks other - List the names of any other networks that are not listed and this resource is involved in
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- networks - List of networks that this datasource is associated with
domain: RWE resources
constraints: reback(conception.Networks, refBack=data sources)
- studies - List of studies that this datasource is associated with
domain: RWE resources
constraints: reback(conception.Studies, refBack=data sources)

data sources

domain: Networks

constraints: ref_array(conception.Data sources)

databanks

domain: Networks

constraints: ref_array(conception.Databanks)

cohorts

domain: Networks

constraints: ref_array(conception.Cohorts)

models - The common data model(s) used by this network

domain: Networks

constraints: ref_array(conception.Models)

studies

domain: Networks

constraints: reback(conception.Studies, refBack=networks)

study requirements - Study requirements

domain: Studies

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study requirements)

regulatory procedure number - Regulatory procedure number, for RMP Category 1 and 2 studies only

domain: Studies

constraints: string

date of signing funding contract planned - Date when funding contract was signed, planned

domain: Studies

constraints: date

date of signing funding contract actual - Date when funding contract was signed, actual

domain: Studies

constraints: date

collection start planned - When was the data collection planned to start?

domain: Studies

constraints: date

collection start actual - When was the data collection actually start?

domain: Studies

constraints: date

analysis start planned - When was the data analysis planned to start?

domain: Studies

constraints: date

analysis start actual - When did the data analysis actually start?

- domain: Studies
 constraints: date
- interim report planned - Planned date of interim report, if expected
 domain: Studies
 constraints: date
- interim report actual - Actual date of interim report, if expected
 domain: Studies
 constraints: date
- final report planned - Date of final study report, planned
 domain: Studies
 constraints: date
- final report actual - Date of final study report, actual
 domain: Studies
 constraints: date
- heading: data - Data management
- data sources - Data sources that provided data into this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: ref_array(conception.Data sources)
- data sources other - Other not listed data sources that provided data into this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: text
- databanks - Databanks that provided data into this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: ref_array(conception.Databanks)
- databanks other - Other not listed databanks that provided data into this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: text
- cohorts - Cohorts that provided data into this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: ref_array(conception.Cohorts)
- cdms - Common data model(s) used in this study
 domain: Studies
 constraints: reback(conception.Mappings, refBack=source)
- study features - Data features
 domain: Studies
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study features)
- data characterisation details - Provide a summary description of the data characterisation or quality check process
 domain: Studies

- constraints: text
- data source types - Types of data sources used
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study datasource types)
- data source types other - Sources of data, if other
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- quality marks - Quality marks, such as ENCePP seal
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study quality marks)
- number of data sources - Total number of data sources included in the study
domain: Studies
constraints: string
- medicines studied INN codes - INN codes of medicines studied
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.INN)
- medicines studied ATC codes - ATC codes of medicines studied
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.ATC)
- medicines studied other - If the medicinal product information (e.g. brand name or active substance or ATC code) does not appear in the available look-ups please enter it here
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- medical conditions studied - Codes of the medical conditions studied
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.MedDRA)
- medical conditions studied other - Codes of the medical conditions studied
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- data extraction date - Date on which the study data was extracted
domain: Studies
constraints: date
- heading: methods - Methodological aspects
- study setting - A short description of the study setting
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- analysis plan - A brief summary of the analysis method (e.g. risk estimation, measures of risk, internal/external validity)

- domain: Studies
constraints: text
- population description - A short description of the study population
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- number of subjects - Estimated number of subjects
domain: Studies
constraints: int
- age groups - Which population age groups are studied
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups)
- objectives - A short description of the study objective
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- interventions - A short description of the study interventions
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- comparators - A short description of the study comparators
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- outcomes - A short description of the study outcomes
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- study design - A brief summary of the study design
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- results - A brief summary of the results of the study on study completion (from abstract)
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- topic - An initial classification of the study purpose
domain: Studies
constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study topics)
- topic other - If the study is not concerning any of the proposed categories, please specify the details
domain: Studies
constraints: text
- trial regulatory scope - Classification of the clinical trial in relation to the medicines authorisation
domain: Studies

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study trial regulatory scopes)

study design classification - Study design classifications

domain: Studies

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study design classification)

study design classification other - Further details on design

domain: Studies

constraints: text

study scope - Scope of the study

domain: Studies

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Study scopes)

study scope other - If scope 'other'

domain: Studies

constraints: text

population of interest - If population of interest is 'Other', please specify which other population has been studied

domain: Studies

constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Population of interest)

population of interest other - If population of interest is 'Other', please specify which other population has been studied

domain: Studies

constraints: text

Table: Studies

Collaborations of multiple institutions, addressing research questions using data sources and/or data banks

Column definitions:

subcohort

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Subcohorts) required

age group

constraints: key=1ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups) required

N total

constraints: int

N female

constraints: int

N male

constraints: int

Table: Subcohorts

Subcohorts defined for this resource

Column definitions:

- resource - Resource this subcohort is part of
 constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required
- name - Subcohort name, e.g. 'mothers in first trimester','newborns'
 constraints: key=1string required
- description - Subcohort description
 constraints: text
- number of participants - Number of participants in this subcohort
 constraints: int
- counts - Total number of unique individuals per age(group), gender and year
 constraints: reback(conception.Subcohort counts, refBack=subcohort)
- inclusion start - Year of first included participant
 constraints: int
- inclusion end - Year of last included participant. Leave empty if collection is ongoing
 constraints: int
- age groups - Age groups within this subcohort
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Age groups)
- main medical condition - Disease groups within this subcohort, based on ICD-10 and ORPHA code classifications
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Diseases)
- comorbidity - Comorbidity within this subcohort, based on ICD-10 classification
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Diseases)
- countries - Countries where data from this subcohort largely originate from
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Countries)
- regions - Geographical regions where data from this subcohort largely originate from
 constraints: ontology_array(CatalogueOntologies.Regions)
- inclusion criteria - Inclusion criteria applied to this subcohort
 constraints: text
- supplementary information - Any other information that needs to be disclosed for this subcohort
 constraints: text

Table: Submissions

Documentation of data submissions related to a resource

Column definitions:

submission date - Date of submission
constraints: key=1datetime required

submitter name - Name of person who submitted
constraints: key=1string required

resources - Resource(s) that this submission is related to
constraints: ref_array(conception.Extended resources) required

submitter email - Email of person who submitted
constraints: string required

submitter organisation - Organisation of submitter
constraints: ref(conception.Organisations)

submitter role - Role of submitter in organisation
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Submitter roles)

submitter role other - Role of submitter in organisation, if other than above
constraints: text

submission type - Type of submission, e.g. 'new entry', 'correction'
constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Submission types)

submission description - Description of the submission, if applicable
constraints: text

responsible persons - List of responsible persons related to this submission
constraints: text

acceptance date - Date submission was accepted
constraints: datetime

Table: Variable mappings

Mappings from collected variables to standard/harmonized variables, optionally including ETL syntax

Column definitions:

source
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

source dataset
constraints: key=1ref(conception.Datasets, refLink=source) required

source variables - Optional, source variable that was mapped from. You may also indicate that a mapping to a target variable was not done and leave this field empty (match = na)
constraints: ref_array(conception.All variables, refLink=source dataset)

source variables other datasets - optional, variable from other source datasets. Initially one may only define mapping between releases

constraints: ref_array(conception.All variables, refLink=source)

target

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

target dataset

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Datasets, refLink=target) required

target variable - in UI this is then one lookup field. In Excel it will be two columns. Value of 'targetVariable' is filtered based on selected 'targetCollection' and together be used for fkey(collection,dataset,name) in Variable

constraints: key=1ref(conception.All variables, refLink=target dataset) required

match - e.g. 'complete, partial, planned, no-match'

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Status details) required

status - whether harmonisation is still draft or final

constraints: ontology(CatalogueOntologies.Status)

description - human readable description of the mapping

constraints: text

syntax - formal definition of the mapping, ideally executable code

constraints: text

comments - additional notes and comments

constraints: text

Table: Variable values

Table definition:

Listing of categorical value+label definition in case of a categorical variable

Column definitions:

resource

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Extended resources) required

variable - e.g. PATO

constraints: key=1ref(conception.Variables, refLink=resource) required

value - e.g. '1'

constraints: key=1string required

label

constraints: string required

order

constraints: int

is missing

constraints: bool

ontology term URI - reference to ontology term that defines this categorical value

constraints: string

since version - When this variable value was introduced if applicable

constraints: string

until version - When this variable value was removed if applicable

constraints: string